

Studies on the Genus Piper—VIII. Further Studies on the Roots of *Piper methysticum* Forst

C. P. DUTTA and UDAY K. SOM

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani-741 235, West Bengal

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The crystalline chalcone isolated from the roots of *Piper methysticum* Forst has been characterised as 4, 4', 6'-trimethoxy-2'-hydroxychalcone(V) from spectral, chemical and synthetic evidence.

In our earlier communications^{1,2,3} we reported the isolation of flavokawain-C(I), methysticin(II), Kawain(III) and Yangonin(IV). Further studies on the roots of *Piper methysticum* Forst culminated in the isolation of another chalcone, *Compound-A*.

On acetylation *Compound-A* furnished a monoacetate, C₂₀H₂₀O₆, m.p. 102-4°, IR band at 1770 cm⁻¹ (acetyl group). The PMR spectrum of the mono-acetate, however, exhibited the characteristic double doublets around δ 6.80 and 7.40 (1H each

I. R=H; Flavokawain-C

V. R=CH₃; *Compound-A*
(Flavokawain-A)

VI. Flavanone

II. R₁=R₂=-O-CH₃-O-

III. R₁=R₂=H

IV. R₁=O⁻H, R₂=H

Compound-A, C₁₈H₁₈O₅ (M⁺, 314); m.p. 110-15° gave a violet colouration with FeCl₃ solution. The negative shinoda test and the characteristic UV absorption spectrum indicated it to be a chalcone having similar chromophoric group as that of flavokawain - C^{2,3}. IR spectrum of the compound revealed the presence of a chelated carbonyl (1626 cm⁻¹), *trans* configuration of -CH=CH- (1608 and 992 cm⁻¹) and 1, 4-disubstituted benzene nucleus (834 cm⁻¹).

The 60 MHz PMR spectrum of *Compound-A*, exhibited characteristic signals for an A₂B₂ system due to four aromatic protons around δ 6.92 and 7.60 (2H, each, d, J=10 Hz). Two narrowly split doublets (J=2 Hz.) around δ 5.97 (1H) and 6.08 (1H) revealed the presence of two *meta* hydrogens in an aromatic nucleus. The sharp singlets at δ 3.83, 3.87 and 3.93 (3H, each) obviously represented the three aromatic methoxyls at slightly different environments. Two *trans* olefinic protons of the chalcone system appeared as a sharp singlet at δ 7.80 instead of the usual double doublets. Finally a sharp one proton singlet at δ 14.34 (disappeared on D₂O exchange) suggested the presence of a phenolic hydroxyl which is *ortho* to the carbonyl⁴.

J=16 Hz.) for α - and β -protons of the chalcone system in addition to the usual singlet for acetate at δ 2.14.

Characteristic mass fragmentation peaks at 207 (M⁺-107) and 181 (M⁺-133) coupled with doublets around δ 6.92 and 7.60, typical of A₂B₂ system suggested the presence of monosubstituted nature of the ring B of the chalcone. *Compound-A* was readily isomerised to the corresponding flavanone(VI), C₁₈H₁₈O₅, m.p. 120-22° with pyridine⁴ IR spectrum of the flavanone exhibited characteristic bands for carbonyl (1630 cm⁻¹) and 1, 4-disubstituted benzene nucleus. PMR spectrum of the flavanone showed chemical shifts characteristic of flavanone having a pair of doublets around δ 6.95 and 7.35 (2H, each, J=10 Hz.) for an A₂B₂ system of 1', 4'-substituted ring B. The protons of the γ -pyrone ring constituted ABX pattern in which AB part (C-3H_{A $\beta\beta$} and C-3H_{B $\alpha\alpha$}) appeared around δ 2.81 and 3.03 as multiplets and the X part (C-2H) appeared as double doublets around δ 5.40.

Based on these spectral and chemical evidences, the structure of the flavanone may be expressed as (VI) which was further confirmed by comparing it

with the monomethyl derivative of the flavanone obtained from flavokawain-C^{2,3}.

Compound-A on boiling with 10% aqueous NaOH furnished 4, 6-dimethoxy-2-hydroxy acetophenone, thereby providing additional and direct chemical evidence in favour of the structure of the *Compound-A* as 4,4',6'-trimethoxy-2'-hydroxychalcone(V) or flavokawain-A⁵. However the identity with flavokawain-A could not be established for want of authentic sample.

Confirmation for the structure (V) assigned to *Compound-A* also received unequivocal support from its synthesis achieved by the condensation of 4, 6-dimethoxy-2-hydroxy acetophenone with *p*-methoxy benzaldehyde in presence of alkali.

Experimental

Air dried pulverised roots of *Piper methysticum* Forst was extracted with light petrol (b.p. 60-80°). The extract upon concentration cooling furnished crude solid which upon chromatographic purification yielded Yangonin, C₁₅H₁₄O₄, m.p. 152-54° and methysticin, C₁₅H₁₄O₅, m.p. 134-36°.

The mother liquor left after the separation of the solid was chromatographed over silica gel when Kawain, C₁₄H₁₄O₈, m.p. 110° migrated out with light petrol. Benzene : Chloroform mixture (9 : 1 and 3 : 1) eluates yielded a further crop of yangonin and methysticin respectively.

The defatted roots were then exhaustively extracted with benzene. The extract was concentrated and chromatographed over silica gel. Benzene : Chloroform (1 : 1) fraction yielded an oily residue which upon purification by preparative tlc over silica gel G with chloroform : methanol (5 : 1) developer, furnished mythesticin and flavokawain-C, C₁₇H₁₆O₆, m.p. 195-96°.

The oily residues obtained after the chromatography of the light petrol and benzene extract respectively were mixed together and rechromatographed over silica gel using solvents of increasing polarity as eluents. Petroleum ether and benzene (3 : 1) eluates afforded *Compound-A*, which was crystallized from ethylacetate and petroleum ether mixture as light yellow coloured needles, m.p. 110-15°. (Found : C, 68.81 ; H, 5.74 ; C₁₈H₁₈O₅ requires C, 68.78 ; H, 5.73). IR : λ_{max}^{Br} 1626 (chelated carbonyl), 1608 and 992 (*trans* - CH=CH-) and 834 (1, 4-disubstituted benzene). PMR : δ : 3.83 (S, OCH₃), 3.87 (S, OCH₃), 3.93 (S, OCH₃), 5.97 and 6.08 (d, J=2 Hz., two *meta* aromatic protons), 6.92 and 7.60 (d, J=10 Hz. Four *ortho* aromatic protons), 7.80 (S, -CH=CH- of chalcone system) and 14.34 (S, disappeared on D₂O exchange, phenolic OH) : Mass 314 (M⁺, base peak), 313 (62.50), 207 (50.00), 181 (45.0), 180 (50.0), 143 (37.5), 134 (75.0) and 121 (97.50) and 69 (25.0).

Acetylation of Compound-A

Compound-A (0.05 g) was dissolved in pyridine (5 ml) and treated with Ac₂O (5 ml). The reaction mixture was heated on a water bath for 4 hours and left at room temperature for 20 hours. The reaction mixture was poured into ice with vigorous shaking when solid separated out. This was taken up in ether (100 ml). The organic layer was made free from pyridine. Solid obtained on removal of ether crystallized from ethylacetate in white needles m.p. 105-6°.

Isomerisation of Compound-A

Compound-A (0.25 g) was dissolved in pyridine (5 ml) and refluxed at 140° in an oil-bath for 8 hours and kept overnight at room temperature. The product was poured in cold water, acidified with HCl (1 N) and extracted with ether. The ether extract upon washing, drying and removal of the solvent afforded gummy residue which was dissolved in benzene and chromatographed over silica gel.

The fractions obtained from petroleum ether : benzene (7 : 3) mixture eluents gave the unchanged chalcone (0.16 g). The solid obtained from petroleum ether : benzene (1 : 1) eluents upon repeated crystallization from petroleum ether-ethylacetate mixture furnished colourless solid of the flavanone (0.07 g), m.p. 120-22°. (Found : C, 68.62 ; H, 5.70. C₁₈H₁₈O₅ requires C, 68.78 ; H, 5.73%).

Alkali Hydrolysis of Compound-A

A solution of *Compound-A* (0.2 g) in 10% aqueous NaOH solution (25 ml) was refluxed for two hours and allowed to stand at room temperature for 15 hours. The product was poured in water, cooled and acidified and extracted with ether. The ether layer on washing, drying and evaporation furnished white solid (0.04 g) which upon crystallization from methanol gave 2-hydroxy-4, 6-dimethoxy acetophenone, m.p. 80°.

Synthesis of Compound-A (Flavokawain-A)

The mixture of 2-hydroxy-4, 6-dimethoxy acetophenone (4.80 g) and anisaldehyde (5 g) was dissolved in ethanol (50 ml) and flashed with N₂ for 15 mins. NaOH (12.0 g) dissolved in minimum quantity of water was then added and the resulting mixture was refluxed on a water bath in N₂ atmosphere for 1 hour. The reaction mixture was kept overnight in an atmosphere of N₂ at room temperature. The product was poured in cold water (200 ml), washed with ether to remove unchange anisaldehyde, acidified and extracted again in ether (250 ml). The ether extract upon washing, drying and evaporation yielded an oily residue which was subsequently crystallized from ethylacetate and petroleum ether mixture in yellowish needles (3.0 g), m.p. 114° (lit⁵. m.p. 114-16°). (Found : C, 68.82 ; H, 5.79. C₁₈H₁₈O₅ requires : C, 68.78 ; H, 5.73%).

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